

Short Communication

Preliminary Evaluation of Bovine Cryptosporidiosis in Kebbi State

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Abstract

The Zoonotic, parasitic diarrhea disease Cryptosporidiosis, is a major constraint to livestock production throughout the tropics and beyond. However, data elucidating its incidence and distribution in cattle have not been sufficiently reported in Northern Nigeria. A cross sectional study on the prevalence of cryptosporidiosis and its distribution in cattle was carried out in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Faecal specimens were collected from 21 locations across the State and examined for Cryptosporidium using formal-ether concentration and modified Ziehl-Neelsen staining technique. A total of 550 cattle were tested for Cryptosporidium, 78 (14.2%) were infected. Age related differences, reveals a significantly higher prevalence in Youngs than adults (Young: 23.0% Vs Adults: 8.1%, $P= 0.046$). Variation in distribution was not gender related (Males: 15.6% Vs Females: 12.7%, $P=0.076$). Cryptosporidiosis in cattle was high in Kebbi State. Infection was higher in calves and this could be a zoonotic transmission route to humans. Improved management system and hygienic practices must be embraced and promoted by owners.

Key words: Cryptosporidiosis, Cattle, Incidence, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Introduction

Cryptosporidiosis is a significant disease in many agro-ecological zones being a serious threat to the livestock economy worldwide (Ayinmode and Fagbemi, 2011). It is recognized as a major constraint to livestock production throughout the tropics and elsewhere (Kinkuotu and Fagbemi, 2014). The infection causes high morbidity and sometimes high mortality rates among domestic animals such as cattle, sheep, goat, pig and horses, resulting in serious economic losses (Nasir *et al.*, 2004; Degerli *et al.*, 2005; Prakash *et al.*, 2009 and Potter and Eshroek, 2010). Being zoonotic, infected animals pose

health risk to humans especially in the immune compromised individuals like people living with HIV/AIDS (Tzipori and Griffiths, 1998). The parasite is one of the major enteric pathogens associated with neonatal diarrhoea in cattle, sheep and goats (Wang *et al.*, 2010). Cattle are reported to be commonly infected with at least two distinct species namely *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Cryptosporidium andersoni* (Olson *et al.*, 1997). Infection is primarily via the fecal-oral route and it takes less than 50 oocysts to infect a healthy animal (Fayer *et al.*, 2000). Ingestion of environmental oocysts results in infection. Oocysts are discharged in the feces of infected animals and are significant in the dispersal and survival of the parasites (Bowman, 2003). The spread of oocysts can be rapid especially when animals are housed communally and overcrowded or from one animal to another via the udders when they are contaminated with infected feces (Nasir *et al.*, 2009). Oocysts are resistant to harsh environmental factors and remain infective for months in cold water, damp or cool environments (Olson *et al.*, 1997). This work aims at determining the prevalence of cryptosporidiosis and its distribution among cattle in Kebbi State.

Materials and Method

Study area

This study was conducted in Kebbi State in North-eastern Nigeria. It is located at approximately latitudes 10° N and 30° N and longitudes 3° E and 6° E. Kebbi State was created on August 27th, 1991. The state was carved out of the former Sokoto State and is made up of 21 local government councils with Birnin Kebbi as the State capital. Kebbi State has a total land area of approximately 37,698 sq. km, with a population of 3,238,630 people (NPC, 2006).

Study Design

It was conceived to conduct a cross-sectional epidemiological survey in Kebbi State, to study the epidemiology of bovine Cryptosporidiosis in the areas. To achieve this, stool specimens of cattle were sampled from twenty one (21) representative locations of the Local Governments in the State. Cattle were randomly sampled from volunteered owners. Pre-tested structured questionnaires were administered both in English and Hausa languages (as preferred by the interviewee). Demographic data for Sex and ages were taken.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval was given by the Faculty of Science Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero. Informed consent was obtained from consenting cattle owners before participating in the study.

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Stool collection and processing

Stool samples were collected from house to house using clean, grease-free, tightly capped, and labelled sterile stool plastic bottles. The field workers visited each home. During the visits fresh rectal faecal samples were collected from each of the animals into a sterile, airtight, 10ml plastic tube. For animals in which rectal sampling was not possible, such as neonates, wooden tong depressors were used to scoop up the superficial layer of faeces without touching the floor. Collected faecal samples were labeled and transported in to the biology laboratory of Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero within twelve (12) hours of collection.

In the laboratory, stool samples were concentrated by formal-ether technique. Briefly using an applicator stick, about 1g of stool sample was placed in a clean 15ml conical centrifuge tube containing 7ml formalin. The sample was suspended and mixed thoroughly with applicator stick. The resulting suspension was filtered through a sieve (cotton gauze) into a beaker and the filtrate was poured back into the same tube. The debris trapped on the sieve was discarded. Then 3ml of diethyl ether is added to the mixture and hand shaken. The content is centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 3 minutes. The supernatant was poured away, leaving only the fine sediment at the bottom of the tube (Cheesebrough, 2005). This was then used to prepare slides for the detection of *Cryptosporidium* Oocysts.

Modified Ziehl-neelsen acid fast technique

Two drops of the sediment was smeared on the slide and air dried. This was fixed with absolute methanol for 1 minute. The slide was flooded with carbolfuchsin for 15 minutes and rinsed thoroughly with water and decolorized with 1% alcohol for 2 minutes after which it was rinsed with water. The smear was then counter stained with malachite green or methylene blue for 1 minute and rinsed with water. This was finally air dried and examined under the microscope using the 40x objective. To achieve better view 10x objectives using oil immersion were used. Where present, *Cryptosporidium* oocysts are round and stain red (Cheesebrough, 2005).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using the version 20 Statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL) on windows 10. Prevalence of infection was presented in percentages. Chi square test was used to compare prevalence by age and gender and to confirm possible association thereof. Associations were considered significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Results

Overall prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* spp in cattle

The analysis showed that 14.2 % (78/550) of the fecal samples analyzed were positive for *Cryptosporidium* Oocysts (Table 1). Generally, the highest prevalence (41.7%) of the infection occurred in Aliero LG, while no case (0%) was recorded in Gwandu, Kamba, Koko Besse and Sakaba LGs (Figure 1).

Prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* spp in cattle in relation to age

The prevalence of cryptosporidiosis in cattle relation to age was observed to be significantly higher ($P=0.047$) in calves (23.0%) than in adults (8.1%). The rate of infection decreased with age.

Prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* spp in cattle in relation to sex

Prevalence with respect sex revealed that infection in males was higher (15.6%) than in females (12.7%); ($P = 0.076$). Infection did not vary with the sex of cattle.

Figure 1: Prevalence of bovine cryptosporidiosis by sampling stations in Kebbi State

Table 1: Distribution of *Cryptosporidium* Oocysts in cattle stratified by age and gender

Parameter	Category	Examined	Infected	% infection	P-value
Overall	All	550	78	14.2	
Age	Young	228	52	23.0	0.046
	Adult	322	26	8.1	
Sex	Male	276	43	15.6	0.076
	Female	274	35	12.7	

Discussion

Cryptosporidiosis is prevalent the world over but with variable levels of infection in different host categories and climatic environments. The overall prevalence of cryptosporidiosis observed in this study is 14.2%. This contrasts with the 22.3% previously reported in North eastern Nigeria (Adamu *et al.*, 2014) and the 78.1% and 37.5% in southwestern Nigeria by Akinkuotu and Fagbemi (2014) respectively. Our results corroborates those in other parts of the world including; 19.2% among calves in Zambia (Geurden *et al.*, 2006), 7.6% in central Ethiopia (Rahmeto-Abebe *et al.*, 2008), 18.5% among cattle in Brazil. It has been suggested that prevalence could be higher in southern parts of Nigeria than in the north due to high rainfall and relative humidity which favours the transmission and survival of the oocysts in the environment (Akinkuotu and Fagbemi, 2014).

The significantly higher occurrence of the infection in young animals have been generally reported by several works (Lefay *et al.*, 2000; Castro-Hermida *et al.*, 2002; Brook *et al.*, 2008; Bejan *et al.*, 2009; Geurden *et al.*, 2006; Pam *et al.*, 2013). The age related differences recorded in this study, could be attributed to the intensive or overcrowded management system with poor sanitary conditions, where cattle of all ages are housed in the same place bringing infected animals together with the healthy ones including young animals whose immune level is low. Animals raised under such confinement will be susceptible to infection from oocyst contamination and transmission (Castro-Hermida *et al.*, 2002; Regassa, *et al.*, 2013).

A number of reports have indicated that, the distribution of *Cyptosporidium* infection is not sex related (Maikai et al, 2011, Adamu et al, 2015). However our finding showed that prevalence was significantly higher in male cattle than in females. The reason for the disparity is not well understood. A possible reason for this, might be due to preferential

practice by famers to feed female cattle with feed from various sources to enhance breeding and milk production.

Conclusion

This study showed that *Cryptosporidium* infection is a high health risk in ruminant animals in Nigeria, particularly calves with female animals. Thus, given these findings, concerted efforts should be directed towards improving our management systems and diagnosis, in order to ensure healthy production of ruminants and reduce possible zoonotic transmission of the parasite in this and similar settings in Nigeria.

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